

Identity and Access Management for ETH ORD Projects

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Goals

Tracking user identity information is crucial in open research data (ORD) for data ownership, data providence, and authorization purposes. Thus, authentication and authorization play an essential role in various ORD services. Furthermore, a lack of compatibility in authentication and authorization was identified by EG-SI as a barrier to integration and interoperability between ORD services in the ETH domain.

This document provides recommendations for ETH services and infrastructure regarding authentication technologies. Projects funded under the ETH ORD Measure 2 are expected to comply with these guidelines.

Recommendations

General Approach

Identity and Access Management (IAM) is a complex topic, and end-to-end implementation can't be offered for all kinds of services. Please consider the recommendations for identity and access before implementing any new service or project. If you know you will have some kind of user in your system you most likely will need authentication and authorization and to ensure that the technology and architectural patterns you will use support that.

Security, while important, must always be deployed in conjunction with proper risk management to avoid over-engineering security controls at the expense of usability. We build technology for users, not for technologists. Since the process of authenticating to and obtaining the rights to use an IT service has no intrinsic value it must be made as unobtrusive as is humanly possible.

Establishing trust between organizations and individuals can be a barrier to ORD; ORD projects should decide how much trust is required. Applications should decide the minimum required level of trust.

Authentication

Services should **utilize federated authentication methods** to allow access from additional institutions. For example, rather than connecting directly to institute-specific active directory instances, services should utilize authentication and authorization infrastructure (AAI). APIs should support delegated authorization to enable interoperability between services.

If possible, always choose the federation that offers the broadest audience. Keep in mind that this implies a limitation in technologies that are provided.

We recommend using **eduGAIN** as the main federation. eduGAIN (Education Global Authentication Infrastructure) is a globally recognized federation that connects national and regional identity federations and thus enables cooperation across national and organizational borders. Users can use their existing credentials (e.g. university or institute login details) to access various services without having to create additional accounts and Single Sign-On (SSO) reduces administrative burden and increases user satisfaction. eduGAIN promotes security standards and provides privacy policies that comply with GDPR and other data protection laws. Also, using trusted identity providers increases the security of authentication. Integration with eduGAIN saves organizations costs by eliminating the need to build and maintain their own authentication and authorization infrastructure and facilitates collaboration between researchers and students worldwide by providing them with access to shared tools and resources.

But if a service requires OpenID Connect or the possibility to enforce Multifactor Authentication (MFA) we recommend using **Switch edu-ID**. The Switch edu-ID is specifically tailored to the needs of Swiss universities and their members, facilitating seamless integration and use within Switzerland. While eduGAIN mainly manages institutional identities, the Switch edu-ID offers a lifelong identity that goes beyond affiliation with a specific institution. This is particularly beneficial for alumni or people who move between different institutions.

The Switch edu-ID offers specific advantages for users in Switzerland, in particular its lifelong validity and the possibility of self-management of data. However, eduGAIN can be advantageous for international cooperation and access to global services. The optimal solution therefore depends on the individual requirements and the desired area of application.

Authorization

The access rights and permissions required by services are likely to be specific to particular use cases.

We recommend deriving authorization information as much as possible from the same sources as authentication, e.g. affiliation information. Avoid relying on any service provider-internal infrastructure or schema (e.g LDAP Groups) to authorize users as this is not scalable. If fine-grained authorization is required, it should be implemented as part of the service itself. This could be implemented as a website or API for delegated right management, for instance. Certain pre-existing groups may need to be included for backwards compatibility.

If the requirements of the ORD community grow to have a common authorization infrastructure, we would recommend implementing the AARC-BPA [Community Attribute Service](#).

Governance

To prevent any misconception the expectations of the users of ORD services using IAM must clearly be defined and communicated. There could be a common part defined by the community and a specific service part defined the specific service owners. We recommend implementing a "Right of Usage" policy which defines the individual rights given to access a service as well as for the access to data. Furthermore, we strongly recommend describing the processes around user registration, granting access as well as revoking access.

Authentication

Identity

Different identity providers offer varying identity information, and verification of the identity information may differ depending on the identity provider (for instance, by validating against a legal name or verifying an email address). Services should generally require the minimal set of attributes possible, both for privacy and to support multiple identity providers.

Identities traditionally were tied to a specific service or organization, with the account inherently granting certain roles and identity information (such as membership in a particular university). Some providers are now shifting to *user-centric* identities, which are intended to remain with a user independent of organizational changes (such as moving universities). Switch edu-ID is an example of a user-centric identity. Independence from a particular organization can enhance the longevity of identity information.

Users may have multiple identities. This can cause confusion when different roles are associated with each identity. The typical solution to this is to allow users to link accounts from multiple identity providers, with the user granted access to services and resources authorized to any of the linked accounts.

Interoperability

Interoperability plays a crucial role in federated identity management for several reasons. Interoperability ensures that users can access multiple services across different domains or platforms using a single set of credentials. This creates a smooth and integrated user experience, as users do not need to remember multiple usernames and passwords for different services. When identity management systems are interoperable, they share security standards, protocols, and practices, leading to more robust security across systems.

Federated identity management systems that are interoperable can more easily scale and adapt to include new services or integrate with other systems. This flexibility is vital for organizations that grow or change over time, enabling them to add or modify services without overhauling their identity management infrastructure. Interoperable systems are typically designed with standard, widely accepted protocols, making them more adaptable to new technologies and innovations in identity management. This helps organizations stay current with technological advancements and prepare for future developments.

Overall, interoperability in federated identity management is essential for creating a secure, user-friendly, and efficient digital ecosystem that spans multiple services and platforms. It supports broader collaboration, reduces redundant efforts in managing identities, and enhances overall system security and compliance. The organizations and projects do not have to provide and take responsibility for secure identity management systems themselves. They can rely on existing secure systems supplied and operated by identity management system specialists.

User Experience

Users, whether in the form of researchers, graduate students, teachers, or administrators, are the reasons we build IT infrastructure of any kind. The authentication and authorization processes are a necessary part of the security and risk management infrastructure of any IT service.

Trust

Trust is the extent to which one party is willing to depend on the other party in a given situation with a feeling of relative security, even though negative consequences are possible. Trust does not derive from technology but is an emergent property of communities. A community in this context means a group of users, organised with a common purpose, and jointly granted access to resources. Communities may act as the interface between individual users and the resources. Trust in this sense means a community's ability to know and determine its users and their permissions. Technology can be used to represent certain aspects of trust (aka technical trust), typically by employing cryptography in various ways. Technical trust (the representation) is often confused with the thing itself. Trust is inherently local.

Authentication protocols

The two main protocols that we recommend are [SAML2](#) (2005) and OpenID [Connect](#) (2014)

- SAML2 is relatively old and is used by a very large number of Identity Providers in organizations, both in Switzerland (SWITCH's AAI Federation) and worldwide (Géant's eduGAIN Interfederation). One of the main strengths of this protocol is its ability to delegate authentication to a third-party Identity Provider, within a federated network. SAML2 requires saving sessions and so is best suited for persistent services such as web applications.
- OpenID Connect (OIDC) is a newer authentication protocol built on the OAuth2 authorization protocol, proposed for example by GAFAM (Google/Alphabet, Amazon, Facebook/Meta, Apple, and Microsoft) to interface their centralized authentication system, or by SWITCH as part of its edu-ID centralized authentication system. [The federative capabilities](#) of this protocol are not yet widely used but will in the future. OpenID Connect also includes workflows which work well for automated or non-web-based use cases (e.g. Authorization Code Flow with PKCE).

Attribute Format

User identity attribute types expressed as SAML attributes or OpenID Connect claims:

Identity Attribute Type	SAML-Attribute	OpenID Connect Claim
-------------------------	----------------	----------------------

Non-reassignable, persistent, unique user identifier	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - subject-id [SAML-SubjectID-v1.0] - pairwise-id [SAML-SubjectID-v1.0] - SAML Persistent NameID [] - eduPersonPrincipalName [eduPerson-202001] - eduPersonUniqueid [eduPerson-202001] - voPersonID [voPerson-2.0] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - sub (public) [OIDC-Core] - sub (pairwise) [OIDC-Core] - eduperson_targeted_id [eduPerson-202001] - eduperson_unique_id [eduPerson-202001] - voperson_id [voPerson-2.0]
Name information	Either (or all) of the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - cn - displayName - givenName + sn 	Either (or all) of the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - name [OIDC-Core] - given_name + family_name [OIDC-Core]
Email information	Either (or both) of the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - mail - voPersonVerifiedEmail [voPerson-2.0] 	Either (or all) of the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - email [OIDC-Core] - email_verified [OIDC-Core] - voperson_verified_email [voPerson-2.0]
Home organization information	schacHomeOrganization [SCHAC-1.5]	schac_home_organization [SCHAC-1.5]
Affiliation	Either (or both) of the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - eduPersonScopedAffiliation [eduPerson-202001] - voPersonExternalAffiliation [voPerson-2.0] 	Either (or both) of the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - eduperson_scoped_affiliation [eduPerson-202001] - voperson_external_affiliation [voPerson-2.0]

Federation Overview

This chapter provides an overview of the various authentication solutions. It is important to emphasize that security precautions such as regular security audits, the use of strong encryption protocols, multi-factor authentication and precise access controls are essential.

As a rule of thumb, relying on an existing authentication, provided by a renowned organization, should be favored over a self-operated or even self-developed authentication system. It relieves one of the responsibilities of providing a stable and secure authentication service.

Available Solutions

This section provides a set of recommendations for authentication solutions for the most common use cases encountered in the context of ORD projects. For each use case, we suggest which authentication, authorization (access management) and service registration methods to employ.

No Authentication

The application/service and all its content are accessible for everyone without the need of registration or identification. Authentication is not needed.

Suitable for publicly accessible information, where no track of who accessed the data is needed.

Authentication: No identity verification or authentication required.

Authorization: No access control; open access to information.

Service Registration: Not needed

Use Case: Publicly accessible information without confidentiality restrictions.

Target Groups General public

Trust Level none

Pros	Cons
No credentials stored	Limitation on confidentiality
No maintenance	No assurance levels
	No data provenance

Application Authentication

The application provider also provides authentication, specifically deployed for this application only or even one that is part of the application itself.

Not recommended. There is no control over the user lifecycle. The typical problem is with (legacy) applications which use ad-hoc identity and access management, for example by creating application-specific credentials for users. When these users leave the institution there is a risk of unauthorized access because their authorization needs to be manually removed by the application manager, a manual step which is easily forgotten.

Generates responsibility for the application provider to manage identity access according to state of the art security standards that are changing over time (hashing algorithm, introduction of passkeys,).

Authentication: Custom authentication methods within the application or systems like keycloak (open source), deployed specifically for this application

Authorization: Application-specific access control defined and managed internally.

Service Registration:

Use Case: Application-specific services requiring customized authentication and authorization.

Target Groups Users who utilize specific applications within an organization.

Trust Level Custom; application responsible for establishing trust

Pros	Cons
Flexibility	Not a federation
Inhouse expertise can be used	Resource intensive
	All users needed in the system
	Security standards might not be present or degrade over time
	Inhouse expertise needed
	Hard to change, when no standards were used.

Institute Authentication

Authentication used by the institute providing the application to manage its employees and a few guest accounts. Normally not intended for users outside of the organization. Therefore, the target group normally does not meet the requirements for open research data, restricting the authentication to users known and managed by the institute.

Warning: We do not recommend this!

Authentication: Use of institute-owned identity providers, typically based on Active Directory or Entra ID.

Authorization: Role-based access control managed by the institute's local authentication.

Service Registration:

Use Case: Management of access to resources and services within a specific institute.

Target Groups Institute members.

Trust Level high (verified by institute)

Pros	Cons
Flexibility	Not a federation
Inhouse expertise	Resource intensive
Full functionality supported by the local authentication system	Limited to local institute
	All external users needed in the authentication system

Self-made Federation (extension of institute authentication)

Warning: We do not recommend this!

At least two local IdPs connected

The internal authentication system is paired with one or more external authentication systems.

Generates responsibility for the application provider to manage identity access according to state of the art security standards, that are changing over time (hashing algorithm, introduction of passkeys,).

Authentication: Connection of at least two local IdPs to extend reach.

Authorization: Central management of access rights across connected IdPs.

Service Registration:

Use Case: Federated services enabling collaboration across multiple institutes.

Target Groups Research groups spread across multiple institutes.

Trust Level

Pros	Cons
Flexibility	Resource intensive
Inhouse expertise can be used	Institute Authentication system
	Governance might not exist (attributes, processes)
	Identity mapping (external to local)
	Security standards might not be present or degrade over time
	Inhouse expertise needed

Switch edu-ID

Authentication provided by Switch for Users for research and education community. Defacto standard for accessing Swiss research applications and services. Hub-and-Spokes architecture with a central IdP and a persistent user-identity with additional attribute verification by institutional IdPs

Authentication: Lifelong, personal, and cross-institutional identity, supported by SAML and OpenID Connect.

Authorization: Must be handled on the application or service level.

- Service Registration:** API/Website for registering the service
- Use Case:** Permanent academic and professional services not bound to institutions.
- Target Groups** Entire academic community in Switzerland, including alumni and external researchers.
- Trust Level** assurance level is documented for each attribute. Some attributes are verified

Pros	Cons
All Swiss academic institutes are included	
Easy to use	Only Switzerland
Established trust	Dependency on SWITCH strategy
Predefined Governance	
Innovative authentication methods (passkeys)	

eduGain

Interfederation service connecting identity federations around the world, simplifying access to content, services and resources for the global research and education community.

- Authentication:** Federated authentication integrating identity services from various countries.
- Authorization:** International access control based on recognized and trusted identities.
- Service Registration:** Services are registered at an identity federation, such as Switch eduID
- Use Case:** International research collaboration and access to global scientific resources.
- Target Groups** Academic users from participating countries and institutions worldwide.
- Trust Level** Core attributes are verified (email, affiliation)

Pros	Cons
Wide coverage of international academic institutes	Limitation on authentication methods
Easy to use	SAML only
Established trust	
Predefined Governance	

UmbrellaID

The authorization system used for the Photon and Neutron community in Europe to authenticate and to authorize. It implements the AARC Blueprint Architecture and utilizes a proxy to do access protocol translation. Existing users from eduGAIN can be used to link to a personal and persistent user identifier. Specific groups can be created ad-hoc and used to identify collaborations. The system is free of cost for services and IdP's and is operated by GÉANT and governed by the ESRF in Grenoble, France and PSI in Villigen, Switzerland.

Authentication:

Authentication can be done via SAML and OIDC IdP's and it comes with a huge set of IdP's. It supports both SAML and OIDC Services as well as the potential for non-web-based services by using RADIUS.

Authorization:

Centrally groups can be created ad-hoc and the groups can be released towards services.

Service Registration:

Pros	Cons
Wide coverage of international academic institutes	Limitation on authentication methods
Easy to use	Standardised and verified attributes
Predefined Governance	
Protocol translation	
Community attributes	

SwissID (Post)

Identity management system provided by the Swiss Post. Used for official Commercial services in Switzerland, such as Swiss Pass.

Not recommended because it is restricted to users from Switzerland.

Service Registration:

<https://www.swissid.ch/geschaeftskunden/login-loesung.html>

CH-LOGIN (eIAM - Bund)

Identity management system provided by the Swiss Government. Supports login with Switch EDU-ID, FedLogin, #edaLogin and a couple more.

For projects financed by the Swiss Government this might be a requirement.

Service Registration:

Google, Facebook, ORCID, CILogon, etc.

Although these systems usually offer an easy to implement API, they have self-service registration and a huge number of users with unvetted attributes and no trust in the identity.

Not recommended due to the lack of trusted identity information.

Authorization

Once a person has been authenticated, it is important to be able to control the user's access to check that they have the necessary authorizations.

Authorization models

The literature classically identifies three main classes of authorization models: *RBAC*, *ReBAC* and *ABAC*.

- **[Role-based access control \(RBAC\)](#)**
The principle is to assign permissions to a role and give the role to a person. For example, a laboratory manager can access his employees' HR data and his laboratory's financial data using his Unit manager role, which contains two permissions "hr-data.access" and "financial-data.access". This is a static model with fine granularity.
- **[Relationship-based access control \(ReBAC\)](#)**
The principle is to model permission using a relationship between the person and the resource, which may well be a hierarchical structure. This model is used on social networks where the user manages people's access to their resources.
- **[Attribute-based access control \(ABAC\)](#)**
This model is used to construct permission rules based on attributes describing the person, the resource accessed, the action to be taken or the work context. For example, if a person is an 'employee', the document is classified as 'confidential' and the user's machine is in the 'intranet', then the person has access to the document. This model is dynamic because it is based on conditions that can change over time.

Modern ABAC authorization systems often include RBAC and ReBAC as special cases. One of the main criticisms of the RBAC model is that it generates a huge number of different roles in complex situations, for example when resources are hierarchical.

The ABAC model, on the other hand, makes it possible to be more concise, but at the cost of maintenance that can become difficult in the face of changing requirements.

Lifecycle

It is essential to have a very clear idea of the lifecycle of permissions within an application so that an auditor can never find permissions that have been granted incorrectly.

- Granting permission: determining who has the right to grant permission and giving them the means to do so.
- Revoking permission: determining who has the legitimacy to revoke permission and giving them the means to do so.
- Check the validity of a permission:
 - automatically delete the permissions of people who have left
 - revalidate the permissions of people who have changed jobs or responsibilities
 - if these checks cannot be carried out automatically, then periodically revalidate permissions and withdraw them when they expire
 - carry out regular audits to check that everything is running smoothly.

This lifecycle management is generally very costly and difficult to carry out in the specific context of an application, and it is preferable to consider an infrastructure dedicated to this as a service.

Application access

Each part of an application, or specific data, can be protected by permissions:

- access to the application: This control can be carried out by the IDP itself, if it is told which categories of users have the right to connect, for example all students from universities A, B and C whose iDPs are trusted, otherwise the application will be open access and available to anyone who can authenticate. After the first access, an identity is often created within the application in order to associate personal data with it.
- access to a part of the application or to specific data, reserved for a specific actor: this control must be carried out after authentication, when the person seeks to access the part concerned
 - If the actor can be identified using an attribute of their identity (for example, their affiliation or origin), this information can be used locally to grant authorization.
 - on the other hand, if the actor is identified by a specific role in the application (e.g. an administrator), you will need to rely on an authorization management service that can perform the necessary checks (OAuth2) and manage the lifecycle of the permissions given) or to manage him locally by hand.

The question to build federated attributes like group membership is part of the AARC architecture, the current status can be found at:

<https://wiki.geant.org/display/AARC/AARC+Architecture>

Limitation: for fine-grained authorization decisions information from within an application is needed and can't be provided by a federation unless a Community Attribute Service is implemented.

Governance

These are recommendations for an acceptable use policy for service providers that should be provided to its users. For a good starting point the Switch edu-ID [Terms of Use](#) can be used.

Right of Usage

The "right of usage" involves setting the legal and organizational frameworks that define how resources, properties, or services may be accessed and used. These are the suggestions:

- a) The availability of the service should be clearly defined. Where possible, broad access should be preferred. (*As open as possible; as closed as necessary.*)
- b) The service providers are responsible for granting access to individual users or groups.
- c) Availability of any service, including identity providers, is not guaranteed and is the responsibility of each individual service.
- d) The right to access a service or data can be terminated if any kind of abuse is detected.
- e) The right to the data remains, if not otherwise stated, with the respective owner of the data and is not transferred to the users of the data.

Data Policy and Protection

We recommend declaring a license for all data published. The license needs to be chosen by the data owner.

For more information see https://www.envidat.ch/#/blog/EnviDat_WSLIntern_2022q4.md

User Registration

- a) User registration happens at the chosen federation. Either by being part of an organization that is part of the identity federation or by self-registration.
- b) It is required that any user has a unique user account that allows
 - a. Uniquely identifying the user
 - b. Contacting the user

Granting Access

- a) The access to services or data in the OpenResearchData initiative can be granted to:
 - a. Individual user accounts
 - b. Groups with individual user accounts
- b) Granting access to data or services is the sole authority of the service provider or the corresponding data owner and may be limited in time.

Revoking Access

Access to services and data can be revoked if:

- a) A user doesn't exist anymore
- b) A service or data doesn't exist anymore
- c) On request by the data owner or service provider
- d) Abuse was detected. Abuse may include (but is not limited to) the following:
 - a. Inappropriate behavior, e.g. defamation, racism, etc...
 - b. Harassment

- c. Using the provided infrastructure for activities not intended by the infrastructure provider, e.g. sending spam, etc...
 - d. Deliberate bypassing of security mechanisms
 - e. Unauthorized commercial use of the infrastructure
 - f. Violations of articles of the applicable criminal code, insofar as these occur intentionally.
- e) Revoking access can be accompanied by civil or criminal charges
 - f) The revocation of access does not need a written form

Implementation Guidelines

The implementation of Switch edu-ID and eduGAIN into your service is very well described on the Switch websites, which can be found [here](#).

Best Practices – Use Cases

Access to publicly available information (Matthias, envidadt)

EnviDat, the Environmental Research Data Portal, developed at the WSL, facilitates public access to the rich reservoir of WSL environmental monitoring and research data. No login is required for accessing most of the data. Nevertheless, accessing restricted data as well as publishing new datasets demand an authenticated user.

Primary Actor: Researcher requires access to publicly available data

Preconditions: None

Implementation: Information is accessible without login on the portal.

Alternate Actors:

- Researcher requires access to unpublished datasets or restricted resources of his organization.
- Researcher requires access to edit existing or create new datasets.

Preconditions:

Researcher needs a valid email account

Implementation:

Researcher can request a onetime login token, using a valid email address. EnviDat generates a one-time login token and sends it to the requesting email address. The token is then used to authenticate the user. At the first token request, EnviDat creates a user profile based on the email address and uses it to store additional information, for example the name of the user. This way, EnviDat has no need to store any credentials. Consequently, EnviDat relies on email security to exchange such login tokens, which can be considered as one-time login passwords. Once a login token has been used once, it cannot be used a second time, and a new token has to be requested again for any future new logins.

By default, new logins do not receive any privileges in the system. Based on the email addresses domain, and when necessary, additional clarifications with group leaders or data providers, EnviDat administrators will manually assign additional privileges. For example, an administrator can grant additional “editor” rights to the account, when necessary for an account to create and publish new datasets. In this manner, the authorization process is tightly controlled, and kept separate from the authentication method.

Access to protected information

(restricted, non-public)

Researcher accessing services

Primary Actor: Researcher requiring access to a general-purpose service offered by the ETH ORD community.

Preconditions:

- The researcher already has an AAI account from a home institution or identity provider supported by the ETH ORD

Infrastructure service accessing services on behalf of the researcher

Primary Actor: Researcher requiring access to a general-purpose service offered by the ETH ORD community.

Preconditions:

- The researcher already has an AAI account from a home institution or identity provider supported by the ETH ORD

Data Repository

This use case is based on the PSI Data Catalog. The catalog is used in a number of ETH-ORD projects.

Actors:

- Researchers deposit data individually
- Beamlines deposit data on behalf of other users
- Collaborators access data securely during an embargo period
- The public accesses open data
- Search engines index and aggregate metadata

Preconditions:

- Researchers already have an eduGAIN account from an academic institution

- Service users are created locally

Implementation:

A number of features are available to public users where no authentication is needed. In order to track data provenance, users are required to sign in for adding data and managing existing datasets. This is done via single sign-on with an eduGAIN account.

While all eduGAIN users are able to authenticate at the service, additional authorization roles must be assigned for access to specific functions. Some roles are automatically assigned based on the user's affiliation while others must be manually granted by administrators through the application. Roles are usually granted to groups, with the group owner being able to manage group members.

Interoperability with other services is achieved in several ways. Services which also use federated identities can be included through a delegated authentication workflow to share information between services (for example, integration with Globus for data transfer). Interoperability with local services (e.g. storage systems) can be done with service users.

Technical:

A keycloak instance is used to track user identities and authorization. This interacts via SAML with a Satsosa proxy, which provides IdP discovery and redirects users to sign in at their home institution. Multiple identities are linked within keycloak and then associated with authorization roles.

Appendix

Definitions

These definitions are aligned with the definitions of the AARC project.

AAI service: A service that enables authenticated and authorized access to resources.

Authentication: The process of verification that the identity of an entity

Access management: Access management refers to the processes and technologies used to control and manage access to information systems, networks, and resources. It is a critical component of information security and risk management strategies in organizations, ensuring that only authorized individuals can access specific resources at the right times and for the right reasons.

Community: A group of users, organised with a common purpose, and jointly granted access to resources. It may act as the interface between individual users and the resources.

Community AAI: An AAI service that also enables the use and management of community identities for access to resources. It comprises three (3) AARC BPA component layers: the Access Protocol Translation, the Community Attributes Services, and the Authorization.

Community identity: A user's digital identity that may be enriched by the community with additional attributes such as a shared user identifier, profile information, and community attributes such as group membership and role information (see [REFEDS-R&S] and [REFEDS-Sirtfi]).

Community service: A service provided to members of a specific community.

Digital identity: Information that represents an entity (subject) within a domain. It contains information about the subject's attributes and relationships.

Entity: A discrete AAI component that can be added in the AAI Federation

Federation: Identity Federation. An association of organizations that come together to securely exchange information as appropriate about their users and resources to enable collaborations and transactions.

Federation member: An organization that has joined the Federation by agreeing to be bound by the Federation Policy.

Federation Operator: Organization providing the infrastructure for Authentication and Authorization to Federation Members.

Federation policy: A document describing the obligations, rights and expectations of the federation members and the federation Operator.

Generic service: A service provided to users, possibly as members of different communities.

Infrastructure service: A service provided by a research infrastructure or e-Infrastructure to members of one or more Community AAI which receives the required attributes through an Infrastructure Proxy.

Identity:

Peer federations: Federations with which the ETH-ORD systems have established transitive trust.

Registry: System used by the Federation Operator to manage entities and their metadata. This may be via a self-service tool or via other manual processes.

Registered representatives: Individuals authorized to act on behalf of the Member. These may take on different roles with different rights attached to them.

Relying Party: A service, site, or entity that depends on an identity provider to identify and authenticate a user who is requesting access to a digital resource.

Application to ETH-ORD projects

The following projects are mandated to follow these guidelines and will receive special coordination:

Program	ID	Title	Applicants	Authentication Requirements
ETH-ORD M2	API-01	Improving the interoperability of Electronic Lab Notebooks and data repositories by enhancing API integration	C. Minotti, PSI B. Rinn, ETHZ S. Baffelli, Empa	Interoperability between SciLog, openBIS, and SciCat
	API-02	Towards a common storage access API	L. Sala, PSI I. Iosifescu Enescu, WSL T. Steiger, ETHZ	Authentication to S3 storage services. Should the mapping between federated identities and S3 tokens be done in the

			A. Bachofner, Empa	application, or is there a better way to do this?
	API-03	Interoperability between the ETH Domain Repositories (IntER)	F. Felder, Eawag C. Minotti, PSI G. Pizzi, PSI I. Iosifescu Enescu, WSL	
	API-04	Reproducibility and Interoperability in Active Data Publication (RI-ADP)	R. Roškar, ETHZ/EPFL I. Iosifescu Enescu, WSL S. Bliven, PSI	Interoperability between Renku, Envidat, and SciCat
	ELN-01	Promoting ELN Adoption and Streamlining Data Interoperability in the ETH Domain	B. Rinn, ETHZ O. Salo, EPFL E. Pratsini, Empa	
ETH-ORD M1	OpenEM	The Open Electron Microscopy Data Network	H. Stahlberg, EPFL S. Bliven, PSI N. Blanc, ETHZ R. Erni, Empa	ETH-wide authentication to scicat Authorization & group management system